
Quantitative evolution method of cracks based on digital volume correlation: A example of granite residual soil

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Abstract:

Crack evolution analyses based on micro-CT scanning are widely used to investigate the microscopic damage of materials under external loading. However, the current crack evolution methods are mostly qualitative or semi-quantitative and have relatively simple indexes, ignoring some three-dimensional spatial information and deficient in crack classification. First, crack classification is essential before the evolution analysis while there are no preferable classification methods. Second, what changes have occurred in the internal micro-cracks of materials under external loading (for example, which cracks present annihilation, regeneration, volume reduction or expansion, split, or merger)? In this work, a crack classification method and a quantitative analysis method for crack evolution are proposed based on the connectivity characteristics of cracks before and after deformation. The cracks are classified into annihilated cracks, neonatal cracks, isolate cracks, split cracks, combined cracks, and compound cracks. The mechanical properties of granite residual soil are complex and have significant anisotropy due to the complex mesoscopic structure. Therefore, we take the CT triaxial shear test of granite residual soil as an example, the three-dimensional displacement fields of the specimen at different loading stages are calculated by the volume correlation method (DVC). Then, the crack positions of the initial state are transformed to the loading stage. Finally, the cracks are classified, and the three-dimensional spatial distribution, volume content, and change are analyzed. The results demonstrate that the evolution of neonatal cracks, split cracks, combined cracks, and compound cracks is significantly related to axial strain. Among them, neonatal cracks are the highest and could well reflect the meso-structural changes during loading.

Keywords: Cracks; Evolution; DVC; CT; Granite residual soil;

1. Introduction

Mechanical property damage has been widely researched in the current geotechnical field. Micro-damage mechanics explores the morphology, distribution, and evolution characteristics of various types of damage from the meso-scale of particles, mineral structure, micro-cracks, and voids in materials. The study of microscopic damage propagation law can provide a crucial experimental foundation for macroscopic damage theory and contribute to the understanding of the failure mechanism of geotechnical materials. In nature, most geotechnical materials are porous media. There are some initial cracks inside the material that difficult to be distinguished by the naked eyes. In recent years, the advanced micro-CT technology could directly measure and reconstruct the microstructure of the material and deepen the understanding of the crack characteristics from the microscopic scale [1-3].

Among the crack evolution methods, the simplest method is qualitatively analysis method by displaying three-dimensional images [4-7]. With the development of image processing technology, some researchers have added pseudo-color information of crack thickness on the three-dimensional crack display [8] or added the pore size distribution curves [9]. Besides, the density change curves of materials were adopted to analyze crack evolution [10-12]. These methods are simple and direct while the abundant information contained by the CT scan could not be fully used. Therefore, the three-dimensional skeleton of the cracks are extracted by the image processing algorithm, and the surface area and intersection points are analyzed to describe the spatial characteristics of the

cracks [13]. The fractal theory was used to quantitatively investigate the three-dimensional crack networks at different loading stages, and the effects of confining pressure and vertical load on crack evolution were compared [14]. Cracks generated by some materials under external loads have significant directionality, and the statistical analysis of crack density and direction could help understand the evolution of cracks [15].

In addition to the geometric analysis of cracks, some researchers have established the damage tensor based on mechanical analysis and combined the microscopic structure quantitative parameters such as crack volume, spatial distribution, and damage area to build the relationship with the mechanical model [16]. The content and distribution characteristics of cracks in geotechnical materials directly affect their permeability. Therefore, the three-dimensional space cracks were abstracted to establish the pore network model and describe the spatial geometric characteristics and topological properties of cracks [17]. Besides, the percolation simulation was conducted to reflect the evolution law of cracks. With the development of digital volume correlation method (DVC), the DVC method has been broadly used to calculate the strain fields of materials during loading. The strain fields were used to estimate the damage fields and analyze the damage evolution of materials [18]. Based on the results of CT reconstruction, the finite element model was constructed and simulated, and the finite element simulation results were compared with the results of DVC calculation to verify the meso-law of cracks [19].

However, these crack evolution methods also have some deficiencies. For example, these crack evolution methods could not fully use the three-dimensional spatial information of cracks. Thus, the following problems that have not been well solved are summarized as follows.

- (1) At present, there are no good suggestions for crack classification while crack classification is the key to analyze crack evolution.
- (2) Which cracks have undergone large changes, such as annihilation, neogenesis, narrowing, expansion, and splitting?
- (3) Which cracks could well effectively reflect the evolution characteristics of the meso-structure of geotechnical materials under external loading?

A representative example is required to explore the quantitative evolution of cracks. We selected granite residual soil as the analysis example. Granite residual soil is widely distributed in the southeast coastal areas of China and has not been transported after weathering of granite [20]. Compared with ordinary clay, the mechanical properties of granite residual soil are more complex and have significant anisotropy due to complex mesoscopic structure [21, 22]. As an abnormal combination of better mechanical properties and worse physical properties under natural conditions [23, 24], it has the disadvantages of easy disturbance, softening in the water, easy disintegration [25], and large intensity variability. These could easily cause disasters such as collapse damage [26] and landslide [27]. These problems are related to the failure behavior of materials. Therefore, the meso-structural evolution of granite residual soil under external loading needs to be well revealed, especially the evolution of cracks. Based on the CT triaxial shear test of granite residual soil, the crack evolution during the loading process is classified and analyzed, as well as the volume change, three-dimensional spatial distribution, and characteristics of different cracks.

2. Quantitative evolution method of crack

2.1. Cracks classification

Micro-CT scanning can obtain the internal microstructure of the material and the internal crack components. The crack evolution law of materials is essential to understand the damage properties of materials. However, it is difficult to effectively reflect the evolution of internal cracks of materials by displaying a three-dimensional image, crack volume content, pore size distribution, and fractal number. For some homogeneous materials, the displaying of three-dimensional reconfiguration is powerless for porous media materials with complex pore structures, though the evolution of cracks can be observed directly through this method. It cannot visually judge and quantitatively

analyze the materials, or the obtained statistical results may lack most of the three-dimensional space information.

Hopefully, we could well obtain the evolution of cracks during the loading process of different materials, such as determining which cracks have changes of annihilated or regenerated, or their volume change. The previous crack analysis methods are difficult to perform quantitative analysis because they could not give a clear and reasonable crack classification method. Therefore, we need to classify cracks clearly and accurately before quantitatively analyzing the evolution of the cracks and calculating the characteristics of different cracks.

Firstly, the evolution of cracks is closely related to their three-dimensional spatial position and volume changes. Thus, the evolution analysis of cracks is also based on the three-dimensional geometric spatial characteristics of cracks. CT scanning can obtain the three-dimensional spatial position of cracks in the material before and after deformation with the voxel as the basic analysis unit. If the cracks before and after deformation are superimposed together, there is a problem of crack connectivity. For example, a crack at the initial stage is not connected with any cracks of after loading stage, or connected with a crack, or connected with multiple cracks. Therefore, the crack connectivity coefficient C is defined as the number of connected cracks of initial stage and cracks after deformation.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, the cracks are classified into six types according to the crack connectivity coefficient C and other important characteristics:

(1) Annihilated cracks: a crack of the initial stage that does not have any connection with the cracks of the loading stage:

$$\forall i, f_i \in \Pi_A \Rightarrow f_i \cap \Pi_B = \emptyset, C_i = 0 \quad (1)$$

where, C_i represents the connectivity number of i crack of the initial stage, Π_A represents the crack group set of the initial stage, Π_B represents the crack group set of the loading stage, f_i represents the number of i crack of the initial stage, and $\cap$ represents the symbol of crack connectivity calculation.

(2) Neonatal cracks: a crack of the loading stage that does not have any connection with the cracks of the initial stage:

$$\forall j, f_j \in \Pi_B \Rightarrow f_j \cap \Pi_A = \emptyset, C_j = 0 \quad (2)$$

where, C_j denotes the connectivity number of j crack of the initial stage, and f_j denotes the number of j crack of the initial stage.

(3) Isolate cracks: a crack of the loading stage that is connected to a crack of the initial stage only for each other:

$$\forall \{i, j\}, f_i \in \Pi_A, f_j \in \Pi_B \Rightarrow f_i \cap \Pi_B = f_j, f_j \cap \Pi_A = f_i, C_j = 1 \quad (3)$$

(4) Split cracks: a crack of the initial stage that is connected to multiple cracks of the loading stage only for each other:

$$\forall i, f_i \in \Pi_A \Rightarrow f_i \cap \Pi_B = \{f_{j_n}\}, f_{j_n} \in \{f_{j_n}\} \in \Pi_B, f_{j_n} \cap \Pi_A = f_i, C_j = 1, N > 1 \quad (4)$$

where, N indicates that the number i crack of the initial stage is split into N cracks, n refers to the subscript of N .

(5) Combined crack: a crack of the loading stage that is connected to multiple cracks of the initial stage only for each other:

$$\forall j, f_j \in \Pi_B \Rightarrow f_j \cap \Pi_A = \{f_{i_m}\}, f_{i_m} \in \{f_{i_m}\} \in \Pi_A, f_{i_m} \cap \Pi_B = f_j, C_j > 1, M > 1 \quad (5)$$

where, M indicates that the number j crack of the initial stage is split into M cracks, m denotes the subscript of M .

(6) Compound cracks: apart from the above five kinds of cracks defined as compound cracks, this kind of cracks is complex and has the following characteristics: 1) the crack belongs to the loading stage and is connected with multiple cracks of the initial stage; 2) the cracks of the initial stage are connected with multiple cracks of loading stage.

The crack classification method is applicable to the cracks of both the initial stage and loading stage.

Fig. 1. Schematic classification of cracks. (color online only)

2.2. Coordinate transformation

The classification method of cracks has been detailed in Section 2.1. However, the premise of this method is that the three-dimensional space position of cracks before and after deformation can accurately correspond. Due to the deformation of the material after loading, the three-dimensional position of cracks has changed, and the cracks in different loading stages could not be directly compared and analyzed. Therefore, we have to accurately transform the initial stage of the cracks to the loading stage before classification. Particularly, the DVC method can accurately calculate the three-dimensional displacement fields of materials after deformation [28], and the granite residual soil has enough speckle quality [29]. Thus, the three-dimensional displacement fields of materials after loading are calculated using the DVC method. Then, the three-dimensional displacement of the initial cracks is transformed to the corresponding loading stage. The coordinate transform equation is:

$$\mathbf{X}' = \mathbf{T} \otimes \mathbf{X} \quad (6)$$

where, $\mathbf{X}$ represents the three-dimensional coordinate of cracks at the initial stage, $\mathbf{T}$ represents the coordinate transform formula, and $\mathbf{X}'$ represents the new three-dimensional coordinate after transform.

The crack evolution analysis process is described as follows.

(1) Reconstruct the CT scanning images and obtain the volume images at different loading stages; select the areas to be analyzed, then, use the DVC method to calculate the three-dimensional displacement field at different loading stages to obtain the displacement fields in x , y and z directions.

(2) Segment the volume images by the threshold segmentation method to extract cracks, and mark the cracks.

(3) Use the three-dimensional displacement fields calculated by step 1 to transform the cracks of the initial stage to loading stages. As presented in Fig. 2, a complex closed three-dimensional surface could be formed since the original regular calculation boundary cannot be maintained any longer after loading. As a result, the cracks in the loading stage cannot match the cracks in the initial stage after transformation. To improve the accuracy of the calculation, we take the complex three-dimensional convex hull surface as the standard boundary and cut the cracks of the loading stage (that is, delete the part of the cracks outside the standard boundary.)

Fig. 2. The calculation domain and bend closed surface. (color online only)

Fig. 3. Analysis flowchart of the evolution of cracks. (color online only)

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(4) Classify the cracks after cutting into annihilated cracks, neonatal cracks, isolate cracks, split cracks, combined cracks, and compound cracks.

(5) Conduct statistical analysis for different kinds of cracks, including volume content, volume change rate, and a three-dimensional display.

The analysis flowchart of the evolution of cracks is exhibited in Fig. 3.

3. Verification and analysis

3.1. CT scan of granite residual soil

We take the CT triaxial shear test of granite residual soil [29, 30] as an example to verify and analyze the crack evolution method in this work. The unloading-step test was used in the CT triaxial test. The photographs of the specimen before and after triaxial shear deformation are shown in Fig. 4(a), and the stress-strain curves and CT scanning points are shown in Fig. 4 (b), and the CT scan system is shown in Fig. 4(d). It is shown that the outer surface of the sample formed a significant fracture surface after shear failure. Fig. 5 illustrates the three-dimensional reconstruction maps of volume images, cracks, and quartz particles at different loading stages. With the increase in axial strain, the specimen appeared significant shear failure, and banded characteristics appeared at the periphery.

Fig. 4. Specimen and stress-strain of granite residual soil: (a) photos of specimen, (b) 4 steps of stress-strain curves, CT scan points labeled as ①~⑤, (c) specimen chamber, (d) CT scan system. (color online only)

Fig. 5. Volume images, cracks and quartz of different loading stages and DVC process. (color online only)

The CT scan images of granite residual soil under different strains are presented in Fig. 6. The distribution of quartz particles in granite residual soil are anisotropic and there is some particle aggregation in the local area. Meanwhile, there are considerable clays in other regions. The parts marked by the red dotted lines have large pores or cracks when the granite residual soil specimen is in the initial state. However, the volume of cracks in the red dotted lines area decreases significantly when the axial strain increases to 4%. This trend gradually decreases with the increasing axial strain. Moreover, there are differences in the three-dimensional displacement at different loading stages, and the differences between the CT scanning images at the same section layer increase as the axial strain increases, making it difficult to observe the differences of cracks at different loading stages.

As indicated in Fig. 7(a), the crack volume decreases significantly as the axial strain increases. The initial crack volume content of the specimen is 3.82%; the minimum value is 2.30% at the axial strain of 8% and then increases slowly with the increasing axial strain. The connectivity index [29] of cracks was calculated, and the variation trend of the index is similar to that of the crack content. Besides, we also calculated the pore size distribution curves of cracks at different loading stages (Fig. 7(b)). Unfortunately, the differences between the pore size distribution curves are not significant, making it difficult to obtain more valuable information from these curves.

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Fig. 6. CT images of the specimen at different positions during triaxial deformation. (color online only)

Fig. 7. Crack evolution distribution curves, (a) crack volume content and connectivity index curves, (b) pore size distribution curves. (color online only)

3.2. Three-dimensional spatial distribution of different cracks

Since the calculation of DVC method is time-consuming, thus, this article refers to the calculation parameters of DVC [29] that the internal voxel block was $1800 \times 1800 \times 1800$, the grid step was 10 voxels, and the sub-volume size of voxels was $81 \times 81 \times 81$. All of the above analyses are based on MATLAB. The three-dimensional displacement fields of the specimen in x , y , and z directions at different loading stages were calculated, as shown in Fig. 8. Then, the cracks of the initial state were transformed into the specified loading stage. Finally, the crack evolution was analyzed according to the methods in Fig. 1 and Fig. 3.

Fig. 8. Displacements at different loading stages. (color online only)

To compare the crack contrast effect under different loading stages, we take No.323 section layer in Fig. 6 as an example, and the results are illustrated in Fig. 9. When the axial strain is 4%, the crack distribution is also similar to that after loading, and there are only some differences in some regions, though there is no three-dimensional space transformation for the initial stage of the crack. With the increasing axial strain, the differences between the distribution of the cracks at the initial stage and after loading are more and more significant, especially the location of characteristic cracks, such as the volume change in some regions. Therefore, severe mistakes would be caused if we directly comparative analysis of cracks.

It can be observed from the superposition results in Fig. 9 that the differences between them decrease significantly after transformation. For example, the positions of the cracks at the initial stage are highly consistent with the cracks after loading. Since the displacement fields calculated by the DVC method are accurate, the superposition could well reflect the change of the cracks. In other words, the 3D displacement field results calculated by the DVC method are reliable and accurate for the 3D transformation of the initial cracks.

Fig. 9. The difference of cracks with-transform and without-transform. (color online only)

According to the proposed crack classification method, the cracks at different loading stages are classified and analyzed, as presented in Fig. 10, Fig. 11, and Table 1.

(1) For the cracks at the initial stage, the volume content of the annihilation cracks increases slowly with the increasing axial strain, with the increment rate for each step of about 1%. The reason is that some cracks with small volume are easily compacted to annihilation at the initial process of triaxial shear, and this trend increases slowly with the increase in axial strain.

(2) For the cracks in the loading stage, the neonatal cracks in the specimen are gradually generated as the axial strain increases. The neonatal cracks in the specimen are less and account for only about 3.72% of the whole crack volume content when the axial strain is 4%. The neonatal cracks increase significantly and the volume content reaches 12.4% when the axial strain is 8%. According to the triaxial stress-strain curves in Fig. 4(b), the specimen was about to soften, which may cause damage. With the increase in axial strain, the softening phenomenon of the stress-strain curves are more significant, and the neonatal cracks in the specimen continue to increase. Besides, the content of neonatal cracks increases from 33.16% to 41.49% when the axial strain increases from 12% to 16%, demonstrating that the specimen has been destroyed.

(3) For isolate cracks at different loading stages, the volume contents only exhibit a slight growth trend, indicating that these local areas were relatively "safe" (that is, they were difficult to be affected by external loading). Therefore, these isolate cracks did not change into larger cracks, or split, or merged into new cracks, while remained

relatively independent.

Fig. 10. Three-dimensional distribution maps of different kinds of cracks under different loading stages. (color online only)

(4) For the split cracks in the loading stage, the volume content has a significant change. The volume content of the split cracks is 8.28% when the axial strain is 4%. The volume fraction of the split crack decreases rapidly to 3.25% when the axial strain increases to 8%, and the attenuation rate reaches 60.7%. Combined with the trend of the stress-strain curve in Fig. 4(b), it can be observed that when the stress-strain curve reaches the peak value, the cracks in the specimen have changed significantly or structurally, and the neonatal cracks also increase significantly. The volume content of split cracks decreases slowly as the axial strain exceeds 8%, suggesting that the local areas of split cracks were easy to be affected by external loading, such as volume shrinkage or expansion and even shear failure.

(5) For the combined cracks at different loading stages, only a small number of cracks are simply combined when the axial strain is 4%, and the volume content is only 0.62%. With the increase in the axial strain, the volume content of combined cracks increases slowly, and the growth rate of volume content is relatively small. On the whole, the cracks inside the specimen are rarely simply combined during loading.

(6) In Fig. 11(a), about 67% of the cracks at the initial stage are compound cracks, and its volume content maintains relatively stable with the increasing axial strain. However, the volume of compound cracks at different loading stages exhibits a significant attenuation trend, indicating that the crack volume is compressed. For example, when the axial strain is 4%, the volume content of compound cracks is 83.54%, and the volume of compound cracks decreases gradually with the increase in the axial strain, which is 79.83%, 58.68% and 51.24%, respectively.

Table 1 Statistical results of different cracks

	Loading stage	NO.1	NO.2	NO.3	NO.4
Total volume content of cracks					
Initial Stage	Annihilated cracks	19.51	21.43	21.10	22.07
	Isolate cracks	4.03	3.20	3.52	3.21
	Split cracks	9.33	6.11	7.25	9.52
	Combined cracks	0.40	0.55	0.66	0.51
	Compound cracks	66.73	68.71	67.47	68.04
Loading stage	Neonatal cracks	3.72	12.40	33.16	41.49
	Isolate cracks	3.84	3.11	4.12	4.05
	Split cracks	8.28	3.25	2.46	1.32
	Combined cracks	0.62	1.41	1.58	1.90
	Compound cracks	83.24	79.83	58.68	51.24

Fig. 11. Evolution distribution curves of different cracks. (a) initial state; (b) loading state. (color online only)

3.3. Volume change of cracks

Besides, it is necessary to analyze the volume change law of themselves to understand the quantitative evolution of cracks in materials more systematically. Therefore, the volume change of each crack was calculated, as presented in Figs. 12~16.

(1) In Fig. 12(a), the volume of annihilated cracks at the initial state increases slowly with the increase in the axial strain. More than 90% of the volume of annihilated cracks are distributed in the range of 10^{-3} ~ 10^{-2} mm^3 , and only a few large cracks are annihilated.

(2) As exhibited in Fig. 12(b), the volume of neonatal cracks under different loading conditions significantly increases. More than 80% of the volume of neonatal cracks are distributed in the range of 6×10^{-4} ~ 10^{-3} mm^3 when the axial strain is 4%. More than 90% of the neonatal cracks are distributed in the range of 3×10^{-3} ~ 10^{-2} mm^3 when the axial strain increases to 8%. Moreover, when the axial strain exceeds 8%, more than 80% of the volume of neonatal cracks are distributed in the range of 10^{-2} ~ 3×10^{-2} mm^3 , and the volume distribution of the cracks corresponding to the axial strain of 12% and 16% is similar.

Fig. 12. Volume distribution curves of annihilated cracks and neonatal cracks at different loading stages. (a) annihilated cracks; (b) neonatal cracks. (color online only)

(3) According to Table 1, there is less correlation between isolate cracks and axial strain, and its volume content remains in a relatively stable range. It can also be observed from Fig. 13 that the volume of isolate cracks is in a slight compression state when the axial strain is 4%; the volume of solitary crack has both compression and expansion when the axial strain is large than 4%. According to the color of the scatter points, most of the cracks with larger volume are in the state of volume compression while the cracks with smaller volume have two states.

(4) In Fig. 14, the split cracks are in the state of volume compression as a whole. When the axial strain is 4%, most of the split cracks with smaller volume are compressed while less split cracks with larger volume are in a compressed stage. When the axial strain increases to 8%, most of the cracks with large volume are in the state of compression, and a small number of cracks with small volume are in the state of expansion. When the axial strain exceeds 8% most of the split cracks with large volume are compressed more significantly, and more and more split cracks with small volume are in a volume expansion state.

(5) As demonstrated in Fig. 15, most of the combined cracks are in the state of expansion as a whole, suggesting that some cracks in the initial stage are merged into one crack and finally increase the volume. Generally, the smaller the volume of the cracks merged, the greater the volume expansion rates. Simultaneously, the number of combined cracks increases with the increasing axial strain. Although the total volume content of combined cracks only accounts for less than 2% of the total volume, it also has a good explanation for the crack evolution.

(6) In Fig. 16, the total volume of compound cracks is generally large while the numbers are relatively small. When the axial strain is 4%, a few cracks with large volume have been significantly compressed, though the stress-strain curve is still in the rising stage. When the axial strain exceeds 4%, the larger the volume of the compound

cracks, the greater the possibility of volume reduction. Meanwhile, some small-volume compound cracks appear volume expansion. This also indicates that most areas of the specimen are in a volume compression state during triaxial shear and in a volume expansion state only in some areas, consistent with the DVC strain field [29].

Fig. 13. Scatter diagrams of volume change of isolate cracks. (color online only)

Fig. 14. Scatter diagrams of volume change of split cracks. (color online only)

Fig. 15. Scatter diagrams of volume change of combined cracks. (color online only)

Fig. 16. Scatter diagrams of volume change of compound cracks. (color online only)

4. Discussion

4.1. Importance and relevance

We have proposed a method and classified cracks into six kinds: annihilated cracks, neonatal cracks, isolate

cracks, split cracks, combined cracks, and compound cracks. Besides, the three-dimensional spatial distribution characteristics of different cracks and the variation of the volume are analyzed. However, which kinds of cracks could better reflect the changes in internal microstructure caused by external loading?

Therefore, the correlation between the total volume of cracks, connectivity index, content changes of different types of cracks, and axial strain increment is calculated. The results are provided in Table 2. Although the correlation between the variation law of the total volume content of cracks and the axial strain increment reaches 0.82, this index is too single to reflect more information about the evolution of cracks. Moreover, there is no significant correlation between crack connectivity index and axial strain, and the correlation coefficient is only -0.24.

Table 2 Correlation coefficients of different cracks to strain

Total volume content of cracks	Connectivity Index of cracks	Annihilated cracks	Neonatal cracks	Isolate cracks	Split cracks	Combined cracks	Compound cracks	For different kinds of
0.82	-0.24	0.87	0.98	0.46	-0.91	0.95	-0.96	cracks

For different kinds of cracks, the neonatal cracks are most closely related to the external load with the correlation index of 0.98. In other words, the neonatal cracks could well reflect the meso-structural changes. The correlation index of compound cracks, combined cracks, and split cracks reaches -0.96, 0.95, and -0.91, respectively. Their evolution law could also well reveal the complex change characteristics of splitting and merging in the material. However, the correlation index between annihilation cracks and axial strain is only 0.87. This could only reflect the compaction of materials in the triaxial shear process not the complex law of meso-structure damage.

To sum up, the crack evolution of neonatal cracks, split cracks, combined cracks, and compound cracks are necessary. They could help us understand the meso-structure evolution law of porous media materials under external loads, which is crucial to the mechanical properties and failure characteristics of materials.

4.2. Method limitation

The proposed method could effectively analyze the crack evolution of geotechnical materials under external loading. However, there are also some limitations. This method is mainly divided into three steps: 1) using the DVC method to calculate the three-dimensional displacement fields; 2) using threshold segmentation method to extract cracks; 3) the classification analysis of cracks, with different calculation steps under different application conditions.

First, the calculation steps of DVC. Since the DVC method has some limitations for the material, the material must have good speckle quality after CT scanning and reconstruction, suggesting that the material cannot be too homogeneous, such as clay or tight shale. The reason is that the gray value distribution of volume images reconstructed by CT scan is too homogeneous and with small gray value gradient. Considering that the differences in gray value (or gradient distribution) could reflect the local characteristics of the structure, homogeneous materials are not suitable for DVC analysis. Ultimately, the method recommended in this work cannot be used to analyze the crack evolution of these materials.

Second, the threshold segmentation method is used to extract cracks. In various CT image processing methods, including threshold segmentation method, watershed method, artificial intelligence method, and even manual segmentation method. However, no matter which CT segmentation method is used, the final and accurate extraction of cracks in the specimen is important before crack evolution analysis, because the inaccurate threshold segmentation results will directly affect the results of crack evolution analysis.

Finally, the crack classification analysis steps. If the cracks in some materials are large and almost all connected, those kinds of materials are not suitable for our recommended method. This is because these cracks are almost connected to form a series of three-dimensional complex networks. It is difficult to accurately determine which cracks have been annihilated or regenerated by the recommended method under external loading. In the loading process, changes may occur only in the local cracks while cannot be identified. Therefore, the proposed method is

not suitable for those materials.

5. Conclusions

In this work, a systematic and quantitative analysis method for crack evolution is proposed based on the DVC method. According to the connectivity characteristics of cracks before and after deformation, the cracks are classified into annihilated cracks, neonatal cracks, isolate cracks, split cracks, combined cracks, and compound cracks. Firstly, the accurate three-dimensional displacement fields are calculated by the DVC method. Then, the cracks in the initial state are transformed to different loading stages and classified. Finally, the statistical analysis and three-dimensional displays of different types of cracks are conducted. These quantitative evolution analyses of cracks are used to deepen the understanding of the evolution mechanism of meso-structure under external loading.

Taking the CT triaxial shear test of granite residual soil as an example, the analysis of crack evolution reveals that there are significant relationships between the evolution of neonatal cracks, split cracks, combined cracks, compound cracks, and axial loading. Additionally, the neonatal cracks are the most closely among them and can well reflect the meso-structure changes of the specimen during loading. However, there is less relationship between the isolated cracks and axial strain.

Acknowledgments

This work is supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant nos. 41877281 and 41372314). We also thanks Zihan Zhang for the help with CT scanning, Engineering Faculty, China University of Geosciences, Wuhan, (China).

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